

Feyzullah Cami of Arta

also known as “Feyzul Cami”, “Mosque of Feyzullah of Arta”

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The mosque was built after the Ottoman conquest of Arta in 1449, but the exact year of its completion is undetermined. Today the mosque is converted to a private house. Signs of architectural alterations and abandonment are evident. According to Seraphim Xenopoulos, a former Metropolitan of the city, this mosque was situated in the muslim neighborhood of Eliyas Bey. The mosque originally had a minaret which was demolished in the 20th century after an unknown event.

Date Range: 1600 CE - 2026 CE

Region: Arta, Greece

Region tags: Greece

Arta is a city in Epirus (NW Greece) with Ancient Greek, Byzantine and Ottoman monuments. The city is near the Ambracian Gulf. Arachthos river is closely connected to the city.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

The society in which the religious place is located is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Notes: An empire at the time of the construction, today a state.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Allah

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Were the structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

– Other [specify]: Local Elites

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– I don't know

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Notes: Not the current usage.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Water source

Notes: The mosque is very close to the river Arachthos

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Other [specify]: Road, concrete features

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Moutzali, Afendra. "Feyzullah Mosque." In *Ottoman Architecture in Greece*, edited by Ersi Broussard. Athens: Hellenic Ministry of Culture Directorate of Byzantine and Post-Byzantine Antiquities, 2008.
- Source 2: Serafeim, Xenopoulos. *Δοκίμιον Ιστορικής Τινος Περιλήψεως Τῆς Ποτε Αρχαίας Και Εγκρίτου Ηπειρωτικής Πόλεως Ἄρτης Και Της Ωσαύτως Νεωτέρας Πόλεως Πρεβέζης Συλλεγέν Και Συνταχθέν ... Υπό Του Μητροπολίτου Ἄρτης Σεραφείμ Του Βυζαντίου* [Brief Historical Essay on the Ancient and Significant City of Epirus, Arta and the Newer City of Preveza, Collected and Compiled by the Metropolitan of Arta, Serafeim of Byzantium]. Athens: Kallous Print, 1884.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Has this place been looted:

– Yes

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 Description: The monument's entry on the official page of the Ephorate of Antiquities of Arta
- Source 2 URL: <http://www.peartas.gov.gr/index.php/episkeftheite/metavyzantina-mnimeia/feyzoyl-tzami>
- Source 1 URL: https://efaart.gr/mnimeia_feizoul/
- Source 2 Description: The monument's entry on the official page of the Region of Epirus

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

Notes: The minaret after 1917.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: A demolished minaret and nowadays housing facilities.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Concrete add-ons

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 41

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Yes

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Plaster

– I don't know

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– I don't know

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Lime

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: No other

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features of the iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Are grave goods present:

– I don't know

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– I don't know

↳ As cenotaphs:

– I don't know

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: No other

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– I don't know

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Supernatural Beings

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Is a supreme high god present:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– I don't know

↳ Do they have another type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ Are they a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Do they have kin relation with elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ other:

–Other [specify]: No other

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– I don't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: Through prayer

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– I don't know

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: It is beleived that God (Allah) is always monitoring.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Does the worship include sex acts/references:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– No

Notes: Not anymore.

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– I don't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– I don't know

Notes: The site is closed to visitors

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Religious Specialists

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– No

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Bureaucracy

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Bibliography

General References

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